

8T – The Grand Field

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October 11, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial coupling constants equation, which already has several forms in the 8T thesis, each express different idea or a use of the equation. In the following paper, the author present in a new form, which stands for the idea of "grand field" which is the gluon field intersecting with all the other Bosonic fields in the coupling.

Introduction

The Primorial equation of the 8T is describing the coupling magnitudes of all known interactions and the interactions which are not yet discovered. In the 8T thesis the primorial is has several forms which are correlated to different uses and ideas of this unique series of dimensionless numbers. In the beginning of the 8T thesis, the even terms of each coupling are correlated to fermions which are two and three divisible to vanish into matter. In this paper, the even terms will represent a direct product of fields, which add up to a one Grandfield, which may or may not have a physical meaning.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

Since the first multiplier is representing the summation of Gluon type, it relates to the strong interaction. We have proven each Boson to be in a state of one to one correspondence with a unique prime. Since the primorial is taking each prime in the set of primes and multiplies it with the Gluon type, we get a term, which contains all the Bosons of the known interactions and the next interactions in line. The following form of the primorial is somewhat more "advanced" as it appears in the end of the thesis but it is identical to (1.1).

$$\left(\mathbf{2}_\mu^{e^-} * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + e^-_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} = \left(\mathbf{2}_\mu^{e^-} \times N_{(V=1)\mu} \times \dots \times N_{(V=k)\mu} + e^-_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

For the first three interactions, we get the term:

$$\mathbf{2}_\mu^{e^-} \times \mathcal{W}_\mu \times \gamma_\mu = (\mathbf{2}e^- \mathcal{W}\gamma)_\mu$$

This idea is very different from the original idea that appeared in the beginning of the thesis and regard the even terms to vanish into nucleons. Rather it shows that there exist one term which contain all the Bosonic 'particles' within it. Since those Bosons are net curvature on the manifold, they belong to the same class, which solidifies that idea of one united field, over an idea of distinct fields for each Boson type. This new interoperation of the primorial many indicate that there is ripples intersection among the Bosons as the arrow of time develops. That makes sense as those higher Bosons come from the original first term $\mathbf{2}_\mu^{e^-}$ as proven previously. In contrast to QFT which has many type of fields which are hard to grasp, 8T aspire to examine those Bosons as excitements or curvature spikes of one entity which is the manifold. The new form of the primorial is expressing that idea. The idea was also presented under the name "Gravity classes" which defined the Bosons to be distinct object of the same class, the curvature class.

$$G_{class} = \{N_V | N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1)\} \quad (2)$$

One last point, In contrast to other theories of physics, the symmetry break of the strong electroweak is something that happens constantly given the Bosons of the three first interactions sums up to the first coupling term:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2}_\mu^{e^-} + 1 &= (\mathcal{W}_\mu + \gamma_\mu) + g_\mu \\ (\mathcal{W}_\mu + \gamma_\mu + g_\mu) &> \mathcal{W}_\mu \cup \gamma_\mu \cup g_\mu \end{aligned}$$

The separation accrues as each element has energy of discrete amount, and all of them unified has higher energy than each as distinct, so first the strong depart, than the Electroweak depart from one another. Gravity is not there as it is the class, which is already broken given the first three distinct elements, which serve as representative of the class. In the 8T it is the mapping between Ricci flow to Energy which set to clarify the ambiguous term of "energy". The universe aspires reaching flatness by the stationarity condition, which is in one to one correspondence for lowest state of energy.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)